

IPBES values assessment

Literature review for the philosophies of good living

Instructions for performing the analysis of the codes

- The main objective of the analysis is to understand what the literature has to say in reference to each of the codes.
- Experts and contributing authors analysing the results can add other potential sub-topics that link the discussion better to your chapters.
- Synthesize the information in the most convenient way. Templates prepared for this purpose can be used to specify the main ideas appearing in the codes each expert is working with, as well as gaps of knowledge, and other cross-cutting topics that might come up in the information coded or in the paper itself, related to Afro-descendant and local communities, gender, economics, NPAs, and so many others, relevant for the assessment.
 - Use the information that has been coded. Refer to columns with excerpts about topics and notes to access more detailed information.
 - It is also possible to reach out to the coder, who might be able to provide quick answers to some of your questions.
 - Go back to the paper only on exceptional circumstances (information is not at all clear, or the coder specified that further details could be obtained from the paper itself).